

Theoretical Calculation Of Global Solar Radiation At Solar Energy Research Center Sokoto, Nigeria Using Temperature Base Model Of Angstrom And Prescott.

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents the global solar radiation in Solar Energy Research Center Sokoto Nigeria. The daily sunshine hour were measured over period of one year from January to December 2023 using angstrom and Prescott model. Daily and monthly average global solar radiation values were calculated. Monthly maximum average daily global solar radiation were 10612.58 KW/m², while the highest daily average global solar radiation of 4601.10 KW/m². From the Calculated data we can see that Solar Energy Research Center Sokoto receive ample global solar radiation and has a very strong potential for solar energy development.

Keywords: Angstrom And Prescott, Global Solar Radiation, Solar Energy Research Center Sokoto Nigeria.

INTRODUCTION

Solar energy research center Sokoto receive stable amount of solar radiation throughout the day. Accurate information on the intensity of solar radiation at a given location is of essential to the development of solar energy-based projects (Islam, 2008). Quantifying solar irradiance that reaches the ground is necessary for many fields of application such as solar energy measurement, agriculture or modeling feeding (World Meterological Organization, 2008). Energy is essential to economic and social development and improved quality of life of human being. Solar energy is being seriously considered for satisfying a significant part of energy demand in Nigeria, as is in the world. Since there is more and more concern on energy conservation and environmental protection, interest has been increasingly focused on the use of solar energy (Muzathik, 2010). Solar radiation which arrives to earth surface for every year is 160 times the world's proven fossil fuels reserves (Ultanir, 1996). The radiation absorption by the ozone layer affects substantially the ultraviolet (UV) interval, while the water vapour attenuates some bounds in the near-infrared (Piedehierro, 2013). In addition to absorption, the scattering by air molecules, clouds and aerosols also contributes largely to the extinction of solar radiation (Piedehierro, 2013).

However, sometimes radiation reaching the Earth's surface can be higher in magnitude compared with its corresponding ideal cloud-free sky (Cede, 2002), (fister, 2003), (Parisi and Downs, 2004), (Sabburg and Calbó, 2009), (de Miguel, 2011). These events are called radiation enhancements, being able to produce

surface solar levels higher than their extraterrestrial value (Piacentini, 2003, 2011), (Antón, 2011). It is easy to say that solar energy is the main, biggest and most important energy resource while the other energy resource are the form of solar energy (Teke, 2014). Solar energy as a clean energy source and one kind of renewable energy is abundant in Nigeria (Muzathik, 2010). Solar energy in the form of PV is already very popular in countries such as the United State, Germany and Japan (Makrides, 2010). Output energy of photovoltaic modules is being estimated by using meteorological data (Teke, 2014). Global tilted irradiance data is needed to estimate output energy of PV modules (Yoshida, 2013) or calculation of diffuse radiation reaching photovoltaic system is essential for simulation of photovoltaic systems (Deb Mondol, 2008). An accurate knowledge of the solar radiation data at a particular geographical location is of vital importance for the development of solar energy devices and for estimates of their performance (Duffie and Beckman, 2006). However it is not possible to measure global solar radiation in many areas due to cost, maintenance and calibration requirements of the measuring equipment whereas sunshine duration is extensively measured in almost all meteorological stations for long period (Teke, 2014). In this respect, the importance of solar radiation data for design and efficient operation of solar energy systems has been acknowledged. A global study has been made on the global solar radiation models available including the study carried out on estimation of the monthly average daily global solar radiation on horizontal surface (Bakirci, 2009). In this study, solar radiation were calculated for a one complete year.

Over the years, many models have been proposed to predict the amount of solar radiation in some cities in Nigeria using various metrological data [Augustine, and Nnabuchi, 2010, Sambo, 1986, Augustine, and Nnabuchi, 2009, Abdul Azeez, 2011]. In this work, the Angstroms and Prescott model is used to estimate the global solar radiation at Solar energy research center, Sokoto state, Nigeria based on the available climatic parameters of sunshine hour.

METHOD AND THEORY

The most convenient and widely used correlation for predicting solar radiation was developed by Angstrom and later modified by Prescott. The Angstrom formula is given by (Sambo, 1986):

$$\frac{H}{H_o} = a + b \left(\frac{S_o}{S} \right) \quad 1$$

Where H (Kw/m²) is the monthly mean daily global solar radiation on a horizontal surface, S(Hour) is the monthly mean daily bright sunshine hours, S_o(Hour) is the maximum possible monthly mean daily sunshine hours, H_o (Kw/m²) is the monthly mean extraterrestrial solar radiation on horizontal surface and *a* and *b* are regression constants given by the equations (Sambo, 1986):

$$a = \left[0.10 + 0.24 \left(\frac{S_o}{S} \right) \right] \quad \text{and} \quad b = \left[0.38 + 0.08 \left(\frac{S_o}{S} \right) \right] \quad 2$$

the monthly mean daily extraterrestrial irradiation H_o and monthly mean day length S_o can be derived from the following formulae:

$$H_o = \left(\frac{24}{\pi} \right) I_{sc} \left[1 + 0.033 \cos \left(\frac{360 D_n}{365} \right) \sin L \sin \delta \left(\frac{2\pi \omega_s}{360} \right) + \cos L \cos \delta \sin \omega_s \right] \quad 3$$

$$\text{Day length } S_o = \frac{2 \omega_s}{15} \quad 4$$

$$\omega_s = \cos^{-1}(-\tan L \tan \delta) \quad 5$$

Where δ is the solar angle of declination and is approximately given as:

$$\delta = 23.45 \sin\left(\frac{360(284 + D_n)}{365}\right)$$

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(Augustine, and Nnabuchi, 2009)

Where n is the day of the year from January 1 to December 31. The value Where: $I_{sc} = 1367Wm^{-2}$ has been recommended for the solar constant (Abdul Azeez, 2011).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The data covered a period of one year (January –December, 2023) for Solar Energy Research Center Sokoto Nigeria located on 13.13318°N latitude and longitude 5.20353°E . The relevant meteorological and solar radiation data calculated using equations (1-6) above presented for the whole period as shown in table below:

Table-1. Monthly mean values of daily solar radiation and the required meteorological parameters for Solar Energy Research Center Sokoto in the year 2023.

MONTH	monthly average global solar radiation (H) in Kw/m ²	monthly average daily extra-terrestrial solar radiation (H _o) in Kw/m ²	monthly average daily bright sunshine hours (S) in hour	maximum possible monthly average daily sunshine hours (S _o) in hour	sunset hour angle (ω _s) in degree	declination angle (δ) in degree	experimental determine coefficient (a)	experimental determine coefficient (b)
January	3997.72	8464.57	6.34	11.32	84.88	20.92	0.2344	0.4248
February	4601.10	10121.20	6.20	11.59	86.92	-12.95	0.2284	0.4228
March	4447.10	10251.70	6.03	11.93	89.44	-2.42	0.2213	0.4204
April	4393.71	10566.73	5.90	12.30	92.22	9.41	0.2151	0.4184
May	4212.13	10612.58	5.70	12.60	94.55	18.79	0.2086	0.4162
June	2021.63	5202.33	5.62	12.76	95.71	23.09	0.2057	0.4152
July	4167.59	10566.93	5.70	12.70	95.19	21.18	0.2077	0.4159
August	3165.02	7803.31	5.78	12.43	93.20	13.45	0.2116	0.4172
September	4349.60	10215.13	5.96	12.07	90.52	2.22	0.2186	0.4195
October	4251.71	9488.31	6.15	11.70	87.74	-9.60	0.2262	0.4221
November	3955.66	8634.92	6.31	11.39	85.42	-18.91	0.2330	0.4243
December	3911.84	8188.90	6.38	11.24	84.30	-23.05	0.2362	0.4254

From Table 1, it is observed that the monthly global solar radiation is not uniform throughout the period of study. Peak radiation is observed in the months of February, March April, May, July and September with values of 10121.20 , 10251.70, 10566.73, 10612.58, 10566.93 and 10215.13 , respectively. On the other hand, the months of June, August, October, November, and December recorded least amount of solar radiation average values of 2021.63, 3165.02, 4251.71, 3955.66, and 3911.84, respectively. This is as a result of the peak period of the cloud cover in sokoto due to the rainy season. In general, higher value of solar radiation is obtained in dry season than wet season. The value of global solar radiation for sokoto town over the period of study is estimated to be 10612.58 using the temperature base model of Angstrom and Prescott.

CONCLUSIONS

The results of this research clearly indicate the main significance of developing temperature base models for estimating global radiation for a particular location. The Angstrom and Prescott model can also be applied to other cities to predict global solar radiation. The global solar radiation intensity predicted in this research can be utilized in construction, analysis and performance estimation of solar energy systems, which is gaining significant contribution in Africa and the world at large.

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